

Thermal Comfort Properties of Rib Knit Structures in Relation to Fibre, Yarn and Fabric parameters

Yamini Jhanji^{1*}, G. K. Tyagi¹, Anupam Kumar² & Deepika²

¹Department of Textile Technology, The Technological Institute of Textile & Sciences, Bhiwani,

²Department of Textile Technology, GZS Campus College of Engineering & Technology, MRSPTU, Bathinda

³Department of Fashion & Apparel Engineering, The Technological Institute of Textile & Sciences, Bhiwani.

Abstract:

Knitted fabrics owing to their excellent stretch ability, good handle and comfort properties are preferred for sportswear, casual wear and intimate wear. Today's consumers seek both comfort and aesthetic appeal while choosing apparels and accessories. Comfort is the predominant factor for clothing layer in immediate skin contact to ensure dry feel next to skin. Therefore, the challenge while designing apparels and accessories entails both functional and aesthetic considerations. A gamut of fibre, yarn and fabric variables influence the comfort aspects of textiles. The present study was undertaken to engineer rib knit structures with varying fibre, yarn and fabric characteristics and designing next to skin accessories thereof. Polyester-cotton blended fabrics exhibited higher thermal resistance, lower thermal conductivity and better moisture vapor transfer properties compared to their viscose-cotton counterparts. Viscose-cotton fabrics on account of their lower thermal resistance, were found to be suitable for summer wear accessories intended for static/low physical activity level. However, PET/C fabrics were found to be suitable choice in cold weather conditions owing to superior thermal properties. PET/C and V/C fabrics showed an increase in thermal resistance and decrease in air permeability and water vapor permeability as the polyester and viscose filament denier was increased. Fabrics developed by feeding two yarns separately through different feeders were found to be more permeable to air and water vapor as compared to their counterparts. Furthermore, the application of antimicrobial finish imparted antimicrobial properties to treated fabrics with more zone of inhibition.

Keywords: Absorptivity, Antimicrobial, Comfort, Conductivity, Permeable, Rib knits, Thermal

Citation: Yamini Jhanji, G. K. Tyagi, Anupam Kumar, Deepika & Ashish Bhardwaj, "Thermal Comfort Properties of Rib Knit Structures in Relation to Fibre, Yarn and Fabric parameters", *Journal of the Textile Association*, **85/3**(Sept-Oct'24), 337-345,

Article Received : 06-06-2024, Revised: 16-07-2024, Accepted: 21-08-2024

1. Introduction

Comfort characteristics of any textile material are associated with thermal and mass transport properties. The fibers, yarn and fabric variables (finishing and printing technique) affect the fabric structure and hence the overall physical and comfort properties of apparels and accessories designed from the engineered fabrics. Finishing treatments influence not only the fabric properties like porosity, air passage but also the aesthetic appeal.

Comfort although a subjective term; is crucial property for clothing. Comfort is related to how an individual feels. There are three main aspects for analyzing fabric comfort. The first aspect of comfort is thermal comfort. Thermal comfort is associated with changes in many physiological and environmental variables like the activity level of the individuals and clothing properties, such as the fabric insulation values and water vapor permeability. Tactile sensation is the second aspect of comfort which relates to skin interaction with clothing as a result of fabric's contact with the skin. Third component of comfort is related to the garment fit [1, 2].

Several factors such as environmental parameters (air and radiant temperature, relative humidity, and wind velocity), the metabolic heat and humidity produced by the human body and the clothing characteristics influence the clothing's ability to transport heat and moisture from the human body and in turn serve as determinants for comfort properties. Satisfactory thermal comfort can be achieved by balance between heat production and heat dissipation. Clothing is considered to be second skin playing a vital role in maintaining thermal balance with environment and providing comfortable state to an individual by maintaining heat balance. Accordingly, different fabrics are being engineered to obtain optimum heat, moisture vapor and liquid transmission through clothing to the outer environment. Knit structures are preferred choice as far as next to skin applications, intimate wear and sportswear are concerned, all of which demand rapid dissipation of heat, moisture and liquid transmission along with certain level of comfort and stretch ability. Rib fabric, characterized by vertical cord appearance, is produced by two sets of needles being alternately set between each other. The applications associated with rib fabrics are innumerable such as socks, cuffs of sleeves and garment borders.

Textile treated with anti-microbial finishes are finding wide spread applications due to the consumers' growing demand and inclination towards comfortable, clean, and hygienic textile products. Textiles undoubtedly provide an excellent medium for the adherence, transfer, and propagation of

*Corresponding Author :

Dr. Yamini Jhanji

Associate Professor, Department of Textile Technology, The Technological Institute of Textile & Sciences (TIT&S), Birla Colony, Bhiwani – 127 021 Haryana

E-mail: yjhanji@gmail.com

infection – causing microbial species to proliferate owing to their characteristics (particularly hydrophilic fibres) and proximity to the human body. Accordingly engineering of textile structures rendering them antimicrobial properties is a big challenge for researchers as tradeoff between handle, comfort properties and aesthetics need to be achieved. Natural fibers are conducive for microbial growth owing to their water affinity. The hydrophobicity of synthetic fibres resists the growth of microbes in these fibres. However, perspiration held in the interstices can provide breeding ground for the microbes [1-3]. Silver is a material with known antimicrobial properties and is generally used to kill bacteria by strangling them in a warm and moist environment. Cell respiration and reproduction gets inhibited as the highly bioactive silver ions bind with proteins in bacterial cell membranes. Along with silver, alginate and chitosan have also been used to make novel antimicrobial materials [4, 5]. Several researchers [6-10] have attempted to engineer different knit structures and compared the structures in terms of their comfort and performance properties.

The thermal properties of single jersey, 1×1 rib and interlock structures were compared by the researchers [6]. They observed that single jersey fabrics had lower thermal resistance and thermal absorptivity and would be warmer to initial touch however relative water vapor permeability of single jersey fabrics was higher compared to double jersey fabrics. Interlock fabrics showed higher thermal conductivity and lower relative water vapor permeability [6].

Similar results were reported in the studies on comfort properties of single jersey and 1×1 rib fabrics [7]. The thermal properties of 1×1 rib fabrics knitted by using various yarns having different properties were studied by researchers [8]. It was observed that yarn properties like yarn count, yarn twist, and combing process of cotton affect different thermal comfort properties of 1×1 rib knitted fabrics. As the yarn twist and yarn count increased, thermal resistance values decreased and water vapor permeability values increased.

It was established by researchers [9] that fabric properties like thickness, aerial density, air permeability and tightness factor determine thermal properties of knitted fabrics. They reported decrease in thermal conductivity and thermal diffusion with the increase in fabric thickness, aerial density and tightness factor.

The literature review reveals that substantial amount of research has been focused towards comfort properties of knit structures. However, there is lack of systematic studies on thermo-physiological characteristics of knit structures which can serve as basis for assessing the suitability of engineered structures for next to skin applications. The present study was therefore undertaken to elucidate the effect of fibre, yarn, fabric variables and finishing treatment on thermal comfort aspects of rib knit structures thereby analyzing the suitability of the engineered structures for design and development of

accessories in intimate contact with skin i.e. socks, gloves etc.

2. Materials

Cotton spun, polyester and viscose filament yarns of varying linear density were used for preparation of rib knit structures. The yarn samples were used for production of ten rib knit structures. Three fabric samples (PC1-3) were constructed in tight, medium and slack construction varying the loop length from 7.5 to 10.3 mm. Four polyester-cotton Fabrics (PC1-PC4) were knitted using polyester filament of 100 denier while the other four samples (PC5-8) constituted of 200 D polyester filament yarn. PC5 and PC8 samples varied in their structure owing to change in the number of feeders (single and double feeder) feeding the yarns for knitting the two samples. Antimicrobial finish applied cotton yarn was used for knitting PC6, PC7 and VC2 fabrics. Yarn and fabric details are provided in Table 1.

All the fabric samples were prepared on KH-323N computerized flatbed knitting machine in Technological institute of Textile and Science, Bhiwani. The machine was equipped with steel feeders, double system with a variably adjustable stroke carriages, computer control with LCD display, and segment needle bed designed for high speed and easy needle replacement.

Table 1 - Details of fabric samples

S. No	Sample Code	Filament Denier/ Yarn count	Finishing treatment	Knit Structure	Loop length (mm)
1	PC1	100D/40 ^S	UT	S.F	7.5
2	PC2	100D/40 ^S	UT	S.F	9.5
3	PC3	100D/40 ^S	UT	S.F	10.3
4	PC4	100D/40 ^S	UT	S.F	9.5
5	PC5	200D/40 ^S	UT	S.F	9.5
6	PC6	200D/40 ^S	AT	S.F	9.5
7	PC7	200D/40 ^S	AT	D.F	9.5
8	PC8	200D/40 ^S	UT	D.F	9.5
9	VC1	225D/40 ^S	UT	S.F	9.5
10	VC2	225D/40 ^S	AT	S.F	9.5

PET-Polyester, V-viscose, C-cotton; S.F-single feeder; D.F-Double feeder, UT – untreated, AT-antimicrobial treated

3. Methods

The prepared fabric samples were tested for their physical properties i.e. course and wale density, aerial density, fabric porosity, loop length and tightness factor.

Course and wale density of test samples was determined by counting the number of courses and wales per centimeter using a pick glass, according to ASTM D 3775-03. The number of courses per cm and wales per cm was determined at ten different positions on the test samples and average was reported for each sample. Fabric thickness was measured on R&B cloth thickness tester at a pressure of 5gf/cm². The test was repeated at ten different positions on the test samples and

average values were recorded. Aerial density of samples was determined according to ASTM D-1059. Fabric porosity (%) was determined using the following equation:

$$\frac{\rho_o - \rho}{\rho_o} \times 100 \dots (1)$$

Where, ρ_o is fiber density in Kg/m³ and ρ , the fabric density in Kg/m³.

Tightness factor of the fabrics was determined using the following equation:

$$\text{Tightness Factor} = \frac{\sqrt{\text{Tex}}}{l} \dots (2)$$

Where, l is loop length in cms.

The prepared samples were evaluated for their thermal properties; namely thermal resistance (TR), thermal conductivity (TC) and q_{max} value on KES-F7-2 Thermo lobo Tester.

AATCC Test method 147-2004 standard was followed for anti-bacterial testing. The parallel stark method was utilized to determine anti-bacterial activity of antimicrobial treated test samples. The average width of zone of inhibition along a stark on either side of the test specimen was calculated using the following equation:

$$W = \frac{(T - D)}{2} \dots (3)$$

Where, W is the width of clear zone of inhibition in mm, T , the total diameter of test specimen and clear zone in mm & D , the diameter of the test specimen in mm.

4. Results & Discussion

The fabric samples were evaluated for their physical and comfort properties and the effect of fibre, yarn and fabric variables on the stated properties were analyzed. Results are presented in the following section. Table 2 shows the physical properties of test fabrics. Thickness varied from 1.30 to 1.67mm while aerial density lied in the range of 167–331 g/m². Comparison of polyester-cotton and viscose-cotton fabrics showed that viscose cotton fabrics exhibited higher aerial density as compared to polyester cotton fabrics. Aerial density decreased from 301g/m² to 168 g/m² as the loop length increased from 7.4 to 10.3 mm. The porosity was observed to increase with the increase in loop length as a consequence of more open structure. Rib knitted fabrics showed variation in tightness factor from 5.1 to 7.9 $\sqrt{\text{Tex}}$ cm⁻¹. Tightness factor showed an upward trend with increase in filament denier and decrease in loop length.

4.1 Effect of fiber type on thermal comfort

4.1.1 Thermal Resistance

Figure 1(a) shows thermal resistance of rib knit structures with two varying fibers-polyester and viscose. Comparison of polyester-cotton and viscose-cotton rib knitted fabrics showed that polyester cotton fabrics exhibited higher

thermal resistance as compared to viscose cotton fabrics. The observed trend may be attributed to the difference in nature of fiber used for fabric production. Higher the fiber conductivity; higher will be the thermal conductivity and hence reduced thermal resistance of fabrics made from such fibers owing to inverse relationship between thermal resistance and thermal conductivity. Viscose fiber with high conductivity (0.06) used to knit viscose cotton fabrics exhibited higher thermal conductivity (Table 3) and hence lower thermal resistance compared to polyester cotton fabrics.

Results were supported by the findings of Tyagi et al. (2008) who observed higher thermal resistance of the polyester cotton fabrics than polyester viscose fabrics.

4.1.2 Thermal Conductivity

Polyester/cotton and viscose/cotton fabrics were compared for their thermal conductivity (Figure 1 b). Thermal conductivity for viscose/cotton fabrics irrespective of finishing treatment was observed to be higher as compared to polyester/cotton fabrics. The observed trend may be attributed to high thermal conductivity of viscose fibre (0.06) than polyester fibre (0.05).

4.1.3 Warm/Cool feeling (Q_{max})

Q_{max} determines the contact temperature of two materials and is the objective measure of warm cool feeling of fabrics on initial brief skin contact. Table 3 and Figure 1(c) shows that viscose cotton fabrics in both cases (treated –VC2 and untreated VC1) have higher q_{max} value than polyester cotton fabrics. The observed trend may be attributed to higher thermal conductivity of viscose-cotton fabrics (Table 3). Hence higher the thermal conductivity; higher will be q_{max} value and such fabrics would be perceived as cooler on initial skin contact.

4.1.4 Air Permeability

Air permeability of textile materials depends on the yarn and fabric constructional variables and bulk properties-particularly thickness, aerial density and porosity. The effect of fiber type on air permeability was studied by varying polyester and viscose fiber. However, no significant difference in air permeability was observed with varying fibertype.

4.1.5 Water vapor permeability

Table 4 and Figure 1(d) shows that viscose cotton fabrics irrespective of finish application showed higher water vapor permeability than polyester cotton fabrics. Water vapor transport may vary according to fiber type based on fiber's hygroscopic nature. The trend may be attributed to higher moisture regain of viscose (11%-12%) as compared to polyester (7.5% to 8) fibre. The statistical analysis of results indicated that there was significant difference between the water vapor permeability of test samples (with confidence interval of 95%).

4.2 Effect of filament denier on thermal comfort

4.2.1 Thermal Resistance

Comparison of polyester-cotton fabrics (PC4 & PC5) with varying filament denier showed that thermal resistance showed an upward trend for polyester cotton rib knit structures (PC5) as the polyester filament denier increased. The observed trend may be attributed to increase in fabric thickness. Fabric thickness by far is considered to be the most influential factor affecting thermal resistance of textile structures and hence the observed trend.

4.2.2 Thermal Conductivity

Table 3 shows thermal conductivity of rib knit fabrics. It was observed that thermal conductivity of polyester cotton fabrics increased as the polyester filament denier increased. The thermal conductivity of the sample fabrics is influenced by fabric aerial density. Results showed that as thermal resistance decreased, thermal conductivity also decreased. This contradiction might be explained by fabric thickness. Fabric thickness decrease as the yarn becomes finer. If the amount of decreases in thickness is more than the amount of decreases in thermal conductivity, thermal resistance decreases as well and hence reduction in the thermal conductivity of fabrics knitted with finer yarns. The results were found to be statistically significant.

4.2.3 Warm/Cool feeling (Q_{max})

It was observed that q_{max} value increased with increase in filament denier for polyester/cotton (PC5) fabrics. The trend may be attributed to increase in fabric thickness and tightness factors (Table 2) with increase in yarn coarseness. It has been reported that fabrics knitted with coarser yarn, irrespective of fiber type have tighter constructions and thus gives a cool feeling at first contact. Univariate analysis of the data showed that the effect of filament denier on q_{max} value was statistically significant at 95% confidence.

4.2.4 Air Permeability

The effect of filament denier on air permeability was analyzed for PET/C fabrics by varying polyester (100D, 200D) filament denier. Air permeability was observed to decrease with increase in polyester filament denier for polyester cotton fabrics. This trend can be attributed to the increase in fabric thickness and corresponding increase in mass per square meter with increase in filament denier. The higher the fabric thickness and mass per square meter (Table 2), more is the resistance offered to passage of air through the fabric and lower is the resultant air permeability. Statistical

analysis of test results showed the effect of filament denier on air permeability to be statistically significant at 95% confidence level.

4.2.5 Water vapor permeability

Table 4 shows that water vapor permeability of polyester/cotton rib fabrics knitted with finer polyester yarn (PC4) showed higher water vapor permeability compared to its counterpart (PC5). The observed trend may be attributed to lower mass per square meter and fabric thickness (Table 2) which facilitates the easy passage of water vapor through above stated fabrics. The statistical analysis of results showed that the effect of filament denier on water vapor permeability was significant.

4.3 Effect of loop length on thermal comfort

4.3.1 Thermal Resistance

Table 3 and Figure 2 (a) shows that thermal resistance increased as the fabric loop length of test samples was increased from 7.5mm to 10.3 mm. Increase in thermal resistance with increase in loop length may be attributed to reduction in tightness factor for slack structure (Table 2). Slack fabrics with longer loop length have more air spaces in the fabric interstices and hence increased thermal resistance owing to higher thermal resistance of air. As the fabric structure become porous with the increase in air volume fraction with the increase in loop length, a corresponding increase in thermal resistance is encountered. A linear equation with positive slope of 0.02, an intercept of 0.16 further supports the relationship between loop length and thermal resistance of fabrics.

4.3.2 Thermal Conductivity

Loop length of the knit construction can also affect its thermal properties as loop length determines the porosity or degree of openness in knitted fabrics. Fabric samples PC1 (tight), PC2 (medium), PC3 (slack) were prepared with varying loop length, while keeping all other parameters constant. Thermal conductivity was observed to decrease as knit structure become slack with increased loop length (Figure 2 b). The amount of fiber per unit area decreases and the amount of entrapped air increases for slacker structures having increased loop length. As the thermal conductivity value of fiber is higher than the thermal conductivity of entrapped air, a decrease was observed in thermal conductivity for fabrics knitted with higher loop length. A linear equation with slope of 1.85 and an intercept of 10.43 with R^2 value of 0.988 indicated negative and linear relationship between loop length and thermal conductivity.

Table 2 - Physical properties of test samples

S. No	Sample Code	Aerial Density (g/m ²)	Thickness (mm)	Fabric Porosity (%)	Courses/ Cm	Wales/ cm	Loop Length (mm)	Bulk Density (Kg/m ³)	Tightness Factor (vTex cm ⁻¹)
1	PC1	301	1.58	87.0	7.48	8.97	7.20	216.54	7.25
2	PC2	311	1.30	91.0	7.48	8.85	9.50	222.14	5.64
3	PC3	168	1.19	91.0	6.61	8.66	10.25	178.72	5.08
4	PC4	223	1.32	90.0	6.61	6.61	7.47	172.86	7.40
5	PC5	167	1.52	87.9	6.69	7.87	8.10	175.78	7.90
6	PC6	170	1.53	88.2	7.20	7.08	10.77	245.00	7.60
7	PC7	304	1.52	90.4	7.08	7.08	10.71	208.21	7.40
8	PC8	331	1.53	90.3	7.20	7.08	10.71	209.90	7.40
9	VC1	217	1.60	83.9	6.29	7.08	9.88	155.00	6.30
10	VC2	217	1.67	84.2	5.51	7.08	10.25	155.00	6.30

Table 3 - Thermal properties of test samples

S. No	Sample code	Thermal Resistance (m ² °C w ⁻¹)	Thermal Conductivity (m ⁻¹ °C ⁻¹ w × 10 ⁻³)	Warm/Cool Feeling (q _{max}) (wsm ⁻² °C ⁻¹)
1	PC1	0.18	8.70	80
2	PC2	0.20	6.50	76
3	PC3	0.22	5.00	58
4	PC4	0.18	6.70	76
5	PC5	0.20	7.60	84
6	PC6	0.20	7.50	79
7	PC7	0.20	5.70	72
8	PC8	0.20	5.50	69
9	VC1	0.18	8.80	104
10	VC2	0.18	8.80	96

Figure 1 - Effect of fiber type on (a) Thermal resistance, (b) Thermal conductivity, (c) q_{max}, and (d) Water vapor permeability

Table 4 - Air permeability & Water vapour permeability of rib knitted fabrics

S. No	Sample Code	Air Permeability (cm ³ /cm ² /s)	Water Vapour Permeability (g/m ² /day)
1	PC1	161.8	1641
2	PC2	202.6	1663
3	PC3	246.8	1707
4	PC4	202.0	1663
5	PC5	141.0	1408
6	PC6	149.0	1430
7	PC7	476.8	1441
8	PC8	480.6	1430
9	VC1	167.0	1519
10	VC2	144.4	1475

4.3.3 Warm/Cool Feeling (q_{max})

Figure 2 (c) shows the effect of loop length on q_{max} . It was observed that slack construction (PC3) would feel warmer on initial skin contact owing to reduction in q_{max} with increase in loop length. It might be attributed to the reduction in stitch density and tightness factor caused by the formation of larger loops as a result of increasing loop length. As compared to smaller loops, larger loops allow less contact points and hence lesser heat transfer from skin to fabric on initial contact. A linear equation with R² value of 0.881 indicated negative and linear relationship between loop length and q_{max} value.

4.3.4 Air Permeability

The effect of loop length on air permeability was analyzed for three fabric samples (PC1, PC, PC3). Air permeability was observed to increase from 161.8cm³/cm²/s to 246.8cm³/cm²/s as the rib knit structure became slack with increasing loop length. The concomitant increase in air permeability of fabrics with increase in loop length (Figure 2d) was due to lower tightness factor (Table 2) or a slacker construction, which allows a relatively free passage of air through spaces within the fabric structure.

Additionally, the porosity (Table 2) of fabrics increased as the fabric loop length was increased. All these factors contribute towards increased values of air permeability for fabrics knitted at longer loop length. Results were found to be statistically significant.

4.3.5 Water vapor permeability

The effect of loop length on water vapor permeability was analyzed for three fabrics prepared with slack (PC3), medium (PC2) and tight (PC1) structures. Comparison of slack, medium, tight fabrics showed that tight fabric was less permeable to water vapor as compared to fabrics knitted at longer loop lengths. Water vapor permeability of fabrics increased with increasing loop length as shown in Figure 2(e). The increase in water vapor permeability of fabrics with increase in loop length may be attributed to lower tightness factor (Table 2) which allows a relatively free passage of water vapor through spaces within the fabric structure. Results were found to be statistically significant.

4.4 Effect of knit structure & finish application on thermal comfort

4.4.1 Thermal Resistance

The effect of knit structure on thermal comfort aspects was studied by developing the test samples (PC5 & PC8 with untreated cotton yarn and P6 & P7 with antimicrobial treated cotton yarn) by altering the feeding of input yarns such that in one case, the two constituent yarns were fed through same feeder (PC5, PC6) and in the latter, feeding two yarns through two separate feeders (PC7, PC8). Comparison of fabrics with varying knit structures and those using antimicrobial treated cotton yarn (PC6 & PC7) showed that thermal resistance of fabrics showed an insignificant difference.

4.4.2 Thermal Conductivity

Thermal conductivity of rib knit structure prepared using double feeder (PC8 & PC7) was lower compared to their single feeder (PC5 & PC6) counterpart irrespective of the finishing treatment as shown in Figure 3(a). The observed trend may be attributed to open structure and high porosity of fabrics prepared using double feeder. The openness of structure allows for more air entrapment. Air being poor thermal conductor, resulted in fabrics of lower thermal conductivity and hence the observed trend. Results were statistically significant at 95% confidence level. It was observed that, finishing treatment did not significantly affect the thermal conductivity of rib knit fabrics.

4.4.3 Warm/Cool Feeling (q_{max})

Comparison of PET/C single feeder (PC5) with PET/C double feeder (PC8) fabrics showed that single feeder fabrics have higher q_{max} value and would be cooler on initial brief skin contact (Figure 3b). The observed trend may be attributed to high tightness factor; lower fabric porosity and higher thermal conductivity of fabrics knitted using single feeder.

4.4.4 Air Permeability

It was observed that feeding the yarns through separate feeders (PC8 & PC7) resulted in fabrics of loose

constructions irrespective of the finish application on cotton yarns. Consequently, such fabrics exhibited higher porosity and air permeability compared to their single feeder counterparts (PC5 & PC6) (Figure 3c). The statistical analysis of results showed that there was significant difference in air permeability of single feeder and double feeder structures.

It was observed that air permeability of viscose/cotton fabrics using finished cotton yarn (VC2) was lower as compared to their unfinished (VC1) counterparts. The effect could conceivably be due to the reduction in inter-yarn space and pore size in the fabric as a result of finishing. However, the effect of finishing treatment on air permeability of PET/C fabrics was found to be statistically insignificant.

4.4.5 Water vapor permeability

Figure 3(d) shows the effect of knit structure on water vapor permeability. Rib fabrics knitted using double feeder (PC8 & PC7) showed high value of water vapor permeability as

compared to single feeder fabrics (PC5 & PC6). The higher value of water vapor permeability of double feeder fabrics for both untreated (PC8) and treated (PC7) fabrics may be attributed to their higher fabric porosity and lower thickness as water vapor transportation would be easier in such fabrics. The statistical analysis of results indicated that there was significant difference between the water vapor permeability of samples (with confidence interval of 95 %).

It was found that viscose-cotton (VC2) samples using antimicrobial treated cotton yarn showed a lower value of water vapor permeability than VC1 samples composed of untreated cotton yarns. The effect could conceivably be due to the reduction in inter-yarn space and pore size in the fabric as a result of finishing. Differences in water vapor permeability value of treated and untreated viscose cotton samples were statistically significant at 95% level. However, the effect of finishing treatment on water vapor permeability of polyester-cotton fabrics was found to be insignificant.

Figure 2 - Effect of loop length on (a) Thermal Resistance, (b) Thermal Conductivity, (c) qmax, (d) Air permeability, and (e) Water vapor permeability

Figure 3 - Effect of knit structure on (a) Thermal Conductivity, (b) Warm/Cool Feeling (q_{max}), (c) Air permeability, and (d) Water Vapor Permeability

Figure 4 shows antimicrobial zone for test sample. It was observed that there was no inhibition zone for fabric samples knitted with untreated cotton yarn (PC5), however inhibition zone was observed for polyester-cotton fabric composed of antimicrobial treated cotton yarn (PC6). The reason might be the action of nano silver acting as antimicrobial agent that kills bacteria by strangling them in a warm and moist environment. Highly bioactive silver ions bind with proteins inside and outside bacterial cell membranes, thus inhibiting cell respiration and reproduction. It can thus be inferred that knit structures rendered antimicrobial by finish application exhibited antimicrobial activity and are suitable for next to skin applications particularly for socks and gloves where the chances of microbial growth owing to sweat generation are prominent.

Figure 4 - Zone of inhibition in antimicrobial treated fabrics

5. Conclusion

Rib knit structures with varying fibre types, filament denier, loop length and knit structures were developed for evaluation of their thermal comfort properties. The effect of finish application on thermal and mass transport properties of developed samples was studied.

Polyester-cotton fabrics exhibited higher thermal resistance, lower thermal conductivity and better moisture transfer properties compared to their viscose-cotton counterparts. Viscose-cotton fabrics are suitable choice for summer wear accessories owing to low thermal resistance in static/low physical activity level. However, polyester-cotton fabrics can be suitable choice in cold weather conditions owing to superior thermal properties.

Polyester-cotton fabrics showed an increase in thermal resistance and decrease in air permeability, water vapor permeability as the polyester filament denier was increased. Use of fine filaments for knitting fabrics intended for summers is thus feasible based on results of the study. Slack fabrics knitted at longer loop length showed higher thermal resistance and would be perceived warmer on initial skin contact owing to low q_{max} .

Varying the knit structure by variation in yarn feeding position resulted in significant difference in thermal and mass transport properties of engineered fabrics. Fabrics developed

by feeding two yarns separately through different feeders were found to be more permeable to air and water vapour as compared to their counterparts. They would be warmer to touch on initial skin contact.

of intimate wear, gloves and socks where wearer encounters moist environment and prone to microbial infection. However, the treated fabrics exhibited lower permeability to air and water vapor.

Fabrics composed of antimicrobial treated cotton yarn showed zone of inhibition and can be used for development

References

[1] G.K. Tyagi, G. Krishna, S. Bhattacharya & P. Kumar, P, “Comfort aspects of finished polyester-cotton and polyester-viscose ring and MJS yarn fabrics”, Indian Journal of Fibre & Textile Research, 31 (137-143), (Jul-Aug'2008)

[2] Y. Jhanji, D. Gupta & V. Kothari, “Comfort properties of plated knitted fabrics with varying fibre type”, Indian Journal of Fiber & Textile Research, 40 (11-18) (2015)

[3] S. M. Landage & A.I. Wasif, “Nanosilver – An effective antimicrobial agent for finishing of textiles”, International Journal of Engineering Science & Emerging Technology, 4(1) (66-78) (2012)

[4] Hes, “Nondestructive determination of comfort parameters during marketing of functional garments and clothing”, Indian Journal of Fiber & Textile Research, 33 (239-245) (2008)

[5] M. Yanilmaz & F. Kalaogolu, “Investigation of wicking, wetting and drying properties of acrylic knitted fabrics”, Textile Research Journal, 32(8) (820-831) (2012)

[6] N.Oglakcioglu & A Marmarali, “Thermal comfort properties of some knitted structures”, Fibers & Textiles in Eastern Europe, 15(5) (64-65) (2007)

[7] O. Demiryurek & D. Uysalturk, “Thermal comfort properties of viloft/cotton and viloft/polyester blended knitted fabrics”, Textile Research Journal, 83(16) (1740-1753) (2013)

[8] N. Ozdil, A. Maramali & S. Kretzschmar, “Effect of yarn properties on thermal comfort of knitted fabrics”, International Journal of Thermal Science, 46 (1318-1322) (2008)

[9] N. Oglakcioglu, P. Celik, T. Bedezute, A. Marmarali & H. Kadoglu, “Thermal comfort properties of angora rabbit/cotton fiber blended knitted fabrics”, Textile Research Journal, 79 (888-890) (2009)

[10] T. Ramachandran, G. Manonmani & C. Vigneswaran, “Thermal behavior of ring and compact spun yarn single jersey, rib and interlock knitted fabrics”, Indian Journal of Fiber & Textile Research, 35 (250-257) 2011

The Textile Association (India)

Membership Fees

Sr. No.	Type of Membership	Membership Fee*
A.	Corporate Member	INR 20,000
B.	Patron Member	INR 4,600
C.	Life Member	INR 3,200
D.	Overseas Member	USD 120
E.	Lifetime to Patron Member	INR 2,000

***Plus 18% GST**